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THE ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS AND DIPLOMACY IN OUR DAILY LIFE

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ABSTRACT. *From early history IR and Diplomacy were seen as abstract ideas making it difficult to understand, however, things have changed after World War 2. For example, the Declaration of Human Rights (10th of December 1948) was signed to ensure perpetual peace and independence among states. In today's world, these two concepts have far more far-reaching influences and play a crucial role in impacting the lives of thousands of people and communities. The main goals of IR and diplomacy are not only preventing wars or conflicts but also providing access to a variety of goods, ensuring healthcare, addressing some global issues, education and opportunities, cooperation among states and developing their economy, and last but not least cultural diversity among nations. By understanding these concepts, states can act better to develop their country, make a great impact on the world, and understand their role in a globalized world. This article highlights the importance of IR and Diplomacy in our daily life.*

KEY WORDS: *International Relations, Diplomacy, Cultural diversity, healthcare, wars and conflicts, economy, agreement, global issues.*

РОЛЬ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ И ДИПЛОМАТИИ В НАШЕЙ ПОВСЕДНЕВНОЙ ЖИЗНИ

АБСТРАКТ. *На заре истории политика и дипломатия рассматривались как абстрактные понятия, затрудняющие понимание, однако после Второй мировой войны все изменилось. Например, Декларация прав человека (10 декабря 1948 года) была подписана для обеспечения вечного мира и независимости*

между государствами. В современном мире эти две концепции оказывают гораздо более глубокое влияние и играют решающую роль в жизни тысяч людей и сообществ. Основными целями международной политики и дипломатии являются не только предотвращение войн или конфликтов, но и обеспечение доступа к разнообразным товарам, обеспечение здравоохранения, решение некоторых глобальных проблем, образование и возможности, сотрудничество между государствами и развитие их экономики, и, наконец, культурное разнообразие между народами. Понимая эти концепции, государства могут действовать более эффективно для развития своей страны, оказывать значительное влияние на мир и понимать свою роль в глобализированном мире. В этой статье подчеркивается важность международных отношений и дипломатии в нашей повседневной жизни.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: *Международные отношения, дипломатия, культурное разнообразие, здравоохранение, войны и конфликты, экономика, соглашение, глобальные проблемы.*

Introduction. Nowadays, "International relations shape everyday life in subtle yet profound ways" (Charles Ray,2020). Not only are they connected to government negotiations and treaties among states, but they also influence the lives of citizens of those countries. Starting from the shelter that we have, the food that we eat, the cars we drive, the clothes we wear, the technology we use, etc all of them are connected to IR. With the help of this concept, countries try to cooperate and exchange goods, some up-to-date products, making them accessible to every humankind. Diplomacy also has a great impact by fostering bonds among state actors, creating long-lasting alliances, addressing global issues, resolving ongoing conflicts, and creating trade. All of these can be achieved through Diplomacy and agreement. This introduction aims to explore how IR and Diplomacy have a great impact on our lives.

To start, availability of goods. A great example can be seen is overseas products. Adidas, Nike, Reebok, Lacoste, Gucci, and others, from cars Tesla, BMW, Mercedes-Benz, and also iPhones and Samsungs which not every country produces original products. So what I mean by that is these products are made in specific states and with the help of international relations and cooperation every country can have access to them. In the past, not everyone could get that product. But nowadays by just sitting at home and using your phone, you can buy them. The only thing left for you is to pay to purchase it and wait to be delivered. There are a variety of different ways to deliver. Like trucks, ships, air cargo, and small vehicles and you don't have to pay extra money for that. Nowadays many countries are trying to set a trade road with others, which is not only beneficial for their economy but also get some fashionable products or maybe

some fruits that cannot be grown in those areas. All of these can be achieved through IR and cooperation.

Literature review. Preventing wars or conflicts. International Relations and Diplomacy provide strategies to resolve and prevent conflicts peacefully. Some countries ally with each other so that in the future they don't go to war, but help each other in every aspect of their life (NATO or UN). There are a lot of organizations that try to keep peace around the world, one of the most notable and powerful is the **UN (United Nations)**, which was founded on the 24th of October 1945 year, takes some peacekeeping missions to operate in all corners of the world, and they help countries to make the transition from war to peace. Also they they can put some sanctions and enforcements on the countries that violate international peace treaties or going war with others. These actions are navigated to force states to stop war and live in peace. Nowadays, in some countries around the world, unfortunately, we can see violations of human rights. To end it we have a concept so-called Human Intervention which goes to places with military force and end violations.

Healthcare. We all know about **COVID-19**, which was a serious disease because of which millions of people died. During that period (starting from 2019) this virus emerged and all countries gathered around one table and searched for solutions. In the beginning, they agreed to close the border to stop the spread of the Virus. Scientists from all over the world tried to create a vaccine and win over it. Moreover, we are facing some global problems which as climate change. There are a lot of cars out there that emit CO₂ and it's not only harmful to the environment but also for living life. To address this issue, many countries agreed to produce e-cars to reduce greenhouse gases. All of these happen with the help of Diplomatic relations among states.

Education. "Internationalization has become a central theme in higher education" (Peterson, 2014,). Some countries use education as a tool to influence the world and build goodwill and it's called "Soft Power". This concept mostly focuses on culture and ideas rather than force. Furthermore, through student exchange programs many students across the globe, have an opportunity to study abroad in IVE League universities namely Stanford, Harvard, Yale, and others. Creating relations between states.

Economy. World Trade Organization (WTO). Through diplomacy, for many countries, it is easier to export or import goods helping their economy grow. Another example is the relationship between the USA and CHINA. Both countries make a huge investment in each other knowing that in the end it is still will be beneficial for both of them. Diplomatic Ties also help create opportunities for foreign people to visit their country. If they are in a good relationship it is most likely that tourists will visit that state which brings money into a country's economy.

Methodology. Last but at least is cultural diversity." Cultural exchange programs can range from tourist holidays to formal political meetings"(Frank J. Ninivaggi M.D, 2024).In these programs, individuals from different countries share traditions and their opinions."For example, when two people hold opposing views on an idea, instead of dismissing each other's perspectives, interpersonal diplomacy permits an engagement in respectful dialogue, actively listening to the other's concerns and differing perspectives. By approaching the discussion respectfully, participants foster an environment where both parties feel valued and understood"(Frank J. Ninivaggi M.D,2024). Through these people can understand and dive into other cultures, and gain more knowledge about the uniqueness of other nations. Another example is traveling by which you meet different people from different cultures. You try to know more about their tradition and slowly you build ties. When you understand that every nation has its interests, values, and identity you will start to respect everyone. All of these that I mentioned earlier can be achieved only peacefully and independently.

CONCLUSION. This article demonstrated the role of IR and Diplomacy in our daily life. So maybe some people think that these two concepts are a little bit difficult to understand, but still, they play a vital role in shaping our modern world. We need to understand that without peace and cooperation, the world that we live in wouldn't be like today. Countries are creating interpersonal bones and signing treaties to develop their country and economy, to improve the lives of their people, and also to exchange ideas and respect each other, through collaboration at least try to solve some global problems and make the world even better.

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